

EFFECTS OF ZnO THIN FILM SURFACE STRUCTURE ON NANOWIRES GROWN BY MOCVD

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1 Abstract

Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanowires (NWs) were grown on ZnO thin films by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) at 600 °C. The ZnO thin films were prepared by metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) at substrate temperatures of 400 – 700 °C at 4 Torr. High-resolution X-ray diffraction measurements showed that the ZnO thin film had a wurtzite structure, with better crystal quality when prepared at higher temperature. The ZnO thin film on sapphire had a uniform 0.1 μm thickness and root-mean-square roughness of 4 – 7 nm in 1 × 1 μm² areas determined by field-emission scanning electron microscopy and atomic force microscopy, respectively.

2 Introduction

GaN-based materials, initially developed by Shuji Nakamura, are important in blue and UV light-emitting diodes and lasers. Similar to GaN, ZnO is an attractive semiconductor with a wide direct band gap ($E_g = 3.36$ eV at room temperature). It has a hexagonal wurtzite structure and can be used in short wavelength blue-to-ultraviolet emitters, such as near-UV lasers and optoelectronic switches [1,2]. ZnO also has useful properties such as good piezoelectric characteristics, high thermal stability, thermal conductivity and high visible and near-infrared transparency [3]. II-VI semiconducting ZnO is a promising material for fundamental light-emitting devices due to its high exciton binding energy of 60 meV at room temperature [4]. It can be grown by various techniques (e.g. magnetron sputtering [5], pulsed-laser deposition (PLD) [6], laser-MBE [7], and metal organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) [8]) on various substrates (e.g. ZnO, GaN, SiC, glass, Al₂O₃, and Si). Al₂O₃ is a commonly used substrate as it is inexpensive and has high stability, despite its high lattice mismatch

with ZnO. MOCVD is suitable for the industrial epitaxial growth of ZnO films [9]. Park *et al.* reported the MOCVD growth of high-quality ZnO films on Al₂O₃ (0001) at 400 – 700 °C [10]. One-dimensional (1D) ZnO nanostructures such as wires, rods, and walls have shown potential applicability in nano-scale optoelectronic devices [11]. Well-aligned ZnO nanowires have been grown by chemical vapor deposition (CVD). Park *et al.* reported the growth of ZnO nanorods and epitaxial layers on GaN by *in situ* MOCVD [12]. The properties of epitaxial ZnO films depend on their growth conditions – e.g. temperature, VI/II ratio, and working pressure [13]. Whether 1D or 2D growth occurs depends on working pressure and temperature, with low pressure promoting 1D growth of nanostructures such as nano-wires, rods, and tubes and high pressure resulting in 2D growth of epitaxial film [4]. However, 2D growth of ZnO film was observed here at low pressure. The effects of growth pressure on the crystalline, optical and surface properties of ZnO have not been fully investigated. Changes of pressure and temperature during deposition can effect changes of growth mode. Homogeneous epitaxial growth is possible [3,13].

This work reports the growth of ZnO nanowires on ZnO thin films. The ZnO thin films were metal-organic chemical vapor deposited on sapphire substrates at 400 – 700 °C at 4 Torr. Increasing the temperature of film deposition resulted in vertically aligned ZnO nanowires.

3 Experimental

3.1 Materials

ZnO thin films were grown by MOCVD on sapphire substrates using diethylzinc (DEZn, Zn(C₂H₅)₂) and deionized water (H₂O) vapor as the zinc and oxygen precursors, respectively. Argon

(Ar) was the carrier gas for DEZn. The ratio of oxygen to DEZn precursors was kept at 3533:1. The flows of DEZn and H₂O were 10 and 20 sccm, respectively, during growth. Working pressure was maintained at 4 Torr and growth for 10 min on Al₂O₃ (001) substrates occurred at 400–700 °C. ZnO nanowires were grown for 30 min on the resulting ZnO films by CVD using DEZn and oxygen gas (O₂) precursors at 2 Torr and 600 °C. The nanowires were 0.6–1.2 μm depending on the film deposition temperature.

3.2 Characterization techniques

3.2.1 FE-SEM

The surface structures of the ZnO thin film and nanowires were observed by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM, Hitachi S-4300, Ligaku).

3.2.2 Morphology

Surface morphology and roughness were investigated by atomic force microscopy (AFM, Autoprobe CP, Park Scientific Instruments) in tapping mode.

3.2.3 High-resolution X-ray diffraction

The ZnO films' structures were characterized by high-resolution X-ray diffraction (HR-XRD) measurements using monochromatic CuKα ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. Standard θ -2 θ diffraction profiles, X-ray rocking curves, and phi scan profiles were measured to quantify the films' crystalline properties and their epitaxial relationships.

4 Results and discussion

FE-SEM images (Fig. 1) show the different structures of ZnO thin film obtained on sapphire substrates. Average film thickness was 100 nm. Grain size increased with increasing temperature. Use of H₂O precursor has been reported to result in larger grains than O₂ [14].

Surface morphology varied with growth temperature (Fig. 2). Root mean square (RMS) roughness measured by AFM was 4.87, 5.83, 6.93, and 7.97 nm, respectively, for growth at 400, 500, 600, and 700 °C. The epitaxial thin film grown at 700 °C showed the greatest surface roughness. High-temperature growth of thin film has been reported to yield overall structural improvement [15].

X-ray diffraction (XRD) in θ -2 θ scan mode was carried out to identify the orientation of the ZnO structures (Fig. 3). The ZnO films were shown to grow with preferred (0001) orientation. Diffraction

peaks were indexed as (002) and (004) wurtzite-structured ZnO. This indicates that the ZnO films mainly grew with preferred (001) orientation on the Al₂O₃ (0001) substrates to minimize surface free energy. A small (101) ZnO peak is visible in the log scale spectrum of the sample prepared at 400 °C; the samples prepared at 500 and 600 °C showed small ZnO (110) peaks. On the other hand, the film epitaxially grown at 700 °C showed only (001) orientation. (002) rocking curves (insets, Fig. 3) were measured to characterize crystalline quality. The curves' full widths at half maximum (FWHM) were 1.5°, 1.04°, 1.3°, and 0.8° for the samples prepared at 400, 500, 600, and 700 °C, respectively. Increasing deposition temperature significantly narrowed the curves' widths. The thin film obtained at 700 °C showed the lowest value, indicative of its high structural quality.

In-plane Φ scan measurements are widely used to examine epitaxial relationships and in-plane orientations of ZnO films [16]. Φ scans of the ZnO (012) planes of the samples grown at different temperatures (Fig. 4) show well-defined six fold symmetry peaks, confirming the hexagonal structure of the unit cells. The six fold symmetry peaks, with 60° separations, demonstrated the in-plane alignment of the ZnO thin films on the sapphire (0001). The ZnO film prepared at 400 °C showed two types of in-plane orientation – it was in transition between orientations. The films prepared at 500 and 600 °C showed only sixfold peaks, though with lower intensities than in the scan of the film deposited 700 °C, which showed better crystalline quality. FWHM of the peaks in the Φ scans decreased 5.19, 4.2, 3.3, 2.38° as substrate temperature increased from 400 to 700 °C, further indicating improved crystallinity at higher growth temperature.

FE-SEM images of ZnO nanowires grown on the different ZnO films show average length increased 0.6, 0.8, 0.9, 1.2 μm as temperature increased from 400 to 700 °C (Fig. 5). The presence of vertically aligned ZnO nanowires (white dots in plan-view SEM images, indicated by circles) increased with increasing film deposition temperature. This implies that the nanowires' size was affected by their growth direction, as the horizontal and vertical directions have different energy states [17]. The initially deposited film acted as a seed layer and there was no lattice mismatch between the film and the ZnO nanowires. The thin film seed layer deposited at 700 °C was epitaxially grown while the other samples showed polycrystalline structures, which

affected the vertical growth of the nanowires. Accordingly, more vertical nanowires grew on the epitaxial ZnO film deposited at 700 °C, which had only [0001] orientation. Unlike the polycrystalline seed layers, the [0001] crystallographic orientation of the epitaxial seed layer was aligned normal to the surface. Therefore, when a tilted nanowire collides with a vertical nanowire, the tip of the tilted nanowire is blocked by the side wall of the vertical nanowire. This collision mechanism plays a key role in the decline in the proportion of tilted nanowires with increasing nanowire length [18]. In accordance with, Increasing the deposition temperature of the ZnO thin film affected its surface structure, which tilted nanowires were declined by increase of the nanowires length.

5. Conclusion

ZnO nanowires were grown on ZnO thin films deposited by MOCVD at 400 – 700 °C. Increasing film deposition temperature improved its crystalline quality, which affected the subsequent growth of vertical nanowires. ZnO nanowires grown on epitaxial thin film deposited at 700 °C were the most vertically aligned. Since ZnO is a promising material for transparent conducting oxide films, well-aligned ZnO nanowires formed on ZnO thin films possess potential applicability in advanced electronic devices and processes. These 1D nanowires on 2D thin film hybrid structures could also be used for nano-scale optoelectronic devices.

Fig. 1 FE-SEM images of ZnO thin film grown for 10 min by MOCVD on sapphire substrates at: (a) 400 °C, (b) 500 °C, (c) 600 °C, and (d) 700 °C. Insets show cross sectional views.

Fig. 2 $1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}^2$ AFM surface images of ZnO thin films grown at: (a) 400 °C, (b) 500 °C, (c) 600 °C, and (d) 700 °C.

Fig. 3 XRD θ - 2θ scans (log scale) of ZnO thin film deposited at: (a) 400 °C, (b) 500 °C, (c) 600 °C, and (d) 700 °C. Insets show XRD rocking curves of the (002) reflection.

Fig. 4 X-ray Φ scans of ZnO thin film deposited on sapphire at: (a) 400 °C, (b) 500 °C, (c) 600 °C, and (d) 700 °C.

Fig. 5 (left) Plan and (right) tilt view FE-SEM images of ZnO nanowires grown at 600 °C for 30 min on ZnO layers deposited at: (a) & (e) 400 °C, (b) & (f) 500 °C, (c) & (g) 600 °C, and (d) & (h) 700 °C. Some vertically aligned nanowires are circled.

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